

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE MANIFESTATION OF DOUBLE NEGATIONS AND MULTIPLE NEGATIONS IN THE SPOKEN ENGLISH OF IMMIGRANTS TO THE UNITED STATES

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Abstract

It is universally believed that people hold negative attitudes towards AAVE, which is thought to be wrong and corrupt the purity of Standard English. This paper is to discuss the unique pattern of double and multiple negations in AAVE.

Keywords: African American Vernacular English; double and multiple negations

1. Introduction

It was recognized a long time ago that black American spoke English differently from the whites. African American Vernacular English is a variety that has set phonological, morphological, syntactic, semantic, and lexical patterns. That is, it is a linguistic and distinct system that is not the same as classroom English, nor is it the same as other varieties of English although it shares features with them, of which double and multiple negation is a unique characteristic of AAVE. This paper is to discuss the unique pattern of double and multiple negations in AAVE.

2. The Unique Pattern of Double and Multiple Negations

This pattern is illustrated in the examples below and grouped in different ways:

(1) a. He can't never help us with our housework.

'He can't help us with our housework.'

b. David don't know nothing.

'David doesn't know anything.'

c. She ain't got none.

'She hasn't got any.'

e. I ain't never seen nobody preach under announcements,

'I have never seen anyone preach while they are giving announcements'

f. Bruce don't want no teacher telling him nothing about any no books.

'Bruce doesn't want any teacher telling him anything about any books.'

g. If you don't do nothing but farm work, your social security don't be nothing.

'If you only do farm work, then your social security isn't usually very much.'

h. Sometimes it didn't have no chalk, no books, no teacher.

'Sometimes there weren't any chalk, any books or any teacher.'

Once you have seen such kinds of sentences mentioned above, the thought of these ones are woeful corruption of English may at least cross your mind. The sentences in (1). (f. g. h.) stop at four, but there is

no limit on the number of negators that can be used. A traditional prescriptive 'rule' in general American English states that double negatives are not grammatical because they make a positive. The formula multiplying two negatives yields a positive does not work for AAVE. The negative meaning of the sentences in (1) is not affected by the addition of negative elements, that is, they do not become positive. This system of negative marking contrasts with the system in mainstream English in that it allows more than one negative element in clauses that are interpreted as negative.

However, in complex sentences, situations are a little complicated. Look at the following examples:

(2). a. Wasn't no girls couldn't go with us.

'All the girls could go with us.'

b. Wasn't no girls could go with us.

'None of the girls could go with us.'

c. Don't nobody pay no attention to no nigguh that ain't crazy.

'If you are a crazy nigger, you will get attention.'

d. Don't nobody pay no attention to no nigguh that's crazy.

'If you are a crazy nigger, you will not get attention.'

e. It ain't nobody I can't trust.

'I can trust everyone.'

f. It ain't nobody I can trust.

'I can trust no one.'

In the complex sentences such as sentences in a, c, e, there are negators in both subordinates, so they are semantically positive. However, one of the subordinates in sentences in b, d, f is positive, so they become negative.

(3). a. Don't nobody want to go to the movies.

b. Do anybody want to go to the movies?

Negative inversion constructions are noted for their superficial resemblance to yes-no questions in that that the auxiliary precedes the subject. Compare the sentences in (3), noting the similarities and differences between the negative inversion

constructions (3a) and the yes-no question (3b). Both of the sentences are grammatical in AAVE. The major difference between the sentences is that (3a) is not a question; it makes an assertion, but (3b) asks a question. This distinction is reflected in the intonation of the sentences. The sentence in (3a) is uttered with declarative intonation, and (3b) has question intonation.

3. Some implications

AAVE is rule-governed and it has a systematic form of communication and has practical application, but they are not always successful in combating negative attitudes towards the linguistic system. Why do people think the English which black people speak was felt to be debased or corrupt? It was also considered to be the result of –and indeed proof –of the inherent inferiority of black people. Black, it was thought, could not speak English properly since they were not capable of it. This view obviously has absolutely no basis in fact. The subject as a whole is in any case fraught with various social and political implications. Language as a powerful commodity that can be exploited by those in power, as well as those who are not, to exclude some and include some.

So statusful are Standard English and prestige accents that they are widely considered to be ‘correct’, ‘beautiful’, ‘nice’, ‘pure’ and so on. Other nonstandard, non-prestige varieties are often held to

be ‘wrong’, ‘ugly’, ‘corrupt’ or ‘lazy’. Standard English, more over, is frequently considered to be the English language, which inevitably leads to the view that other varieties of English are some kind of deviation from a norm, the deviation being due to laziness, ignorance or lack of intelligence.

4. Conclusion

Linguistically speaking, all languages are equally good as linguistic systems. There is no such thing as a pure language. All languages are subject to change, and they are all the product of influence and admixture from other languages. In each case, linguistic inequality can be seen as a cause (along with many other factor, of course) of social inequality, but also as a sequence of it.

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